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ABSTRACT BOOK

ENHANCEMENT OF CLINDAMYCIN HYDROCHLORIDE DISSOLUTION RATE USING BILE ACIDS IN HYDROGEL PHARMACEUTICAL FORMULATIONS

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Introduction: Clindamycin hydrochloride is a widely used antibiotic in therapy of mild to moderate cases of acne and skin infections. Although widely used in dermatology, the major issue of conventional clindamycin topical formulations for effective treatment is the hydrophilic nature of clindamycin, not suitable for skin penetration and accumulation in the pilosebaceous structures. Therefore, new approaches in the development of clindamycin topical formulations are of great importance and several vesicular and particulate nanodelivery systems of clindamycin have been developed.¹ The use of bile acids as penetration enhancers in both conventional dosage forms and novel drug delivery systems has been increasingly investigated due to their biocompatibility and specific physicochemical properties.² To the best of our knowledge, topical formulations of clindamycin with bile acids have not been previously investigated.

Objectives: The aim of this study was to formulate 1% clindamycin hydrogel formulations for topical application with good physical properties and adequate release of the active substance, as well as to investigate the effects of the type of gelling agent, the type and concentration of bile acids as penetration enhancers, on the clindamycin dissolution rate using in vitro model.

Materials and Methods: Eight formulations of 1% clindamycin hydrochloride gel were prepared with two different gelling agents, two different bile acids as permeation enhancers in two different concentrations, adapting a 23 full factorial design. Carbomer 940 and carmellose sodium were used as gelling agents. The release and permeation enhancers in the hydrogel formulations were deoxycholic acid and cholic acid in concentrations of 0.1% and 0.5%. The hydrogels were evaluated for physical appearance, pH, drug content, drug release, and permeability parameters. An in vitro release test of clindamycin hydrochloride from hydrogel formulations was performed in an apparatus, resembling a Franz diffusion cell, containing a cellulose dialysis membrane. The amount of the drug released and permeated per unit surface area ($\mu\text{g}/\text{cm}^2$) was plotted versus time (hours). The values of clindamycin permeability parameters in different formulations were calculated from dissolution curves. The interactions of clindamycin hydrochloride and bile acids were investigated also by molecular mechanics calculations (MM2).

Results and Discussion: Although formulations with carbomer as the gelling agent exerted optimal sensory properties, carmellose sodium hydrogels had significantly higher release rates and permeation of clindamycin hydrochloride. The permeability of clindamycin increased with the addition of bile acids, particularly after the addition of cholic acid in a higher concentration. Similarly, the permeability of clindamycin in carmellose sodium gels increased with the addition of bile acids. It was more pronounced after the addition of cholic acid than deoxycholic acid, and slightly more after the addition of cholic acid at a higher concentration in comparison to a lower concentration. Following the molecular mechanics calculations, it was shown that the total energies of both clindamycin/bile acid complexes were lower than the sum of the potential energies of the two single components optimized by molecular mechanics calculations, indicating that the formation of the complexes induced a stabilization of the system. Clindamycin/cholic acid complex was demonstrated to be more stable in comparison to the clindamycin/deoxycholic acid complex.

Conclusions: The type and concentration of bile acid affect the dissolution rate and permeation of clindamycin. In summary, the hydrogel containing carmellose sodium as a gelling agent and 0.1% cholic acid as a penetration enhancer can be considered as the formulation of choice.

References:

1. Fatima N *et al.*, *Journal of Drug Delivery Science and Technology*. 54, 101253 (2019).
2. Pavlović N *et al.*, *Frontiers in Pharmacology*. 9, 1283 (2018).

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